

Turning Big Data Into Actionable Intelligence

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Abstract

Supply chain managers are tasked with ensuring the efficient movement of all freight. When the supply chain process becomes more and more complex, there exists an opportunity to develop costly kinks to make the process manageable. Establishing key performance indicators (KPIs) is an one way transportation and it can also monitor performance and strive for solutions to save money. But KPIs are considered as a single piece of an unsolved puzzle. Within the company's transportation management system (TMS), exists the information which can help the managers to make better business decisions. This process is called actionable intelligence. The quantity of data a transportation management system can provide depends on a number of factors including years of data collected, whether the system is cloud-based or on-premise. This paper will explore how the data/information saved in a transportation management system can be turned into information managers which in turn can act upon to improve supply chain performance.

Keywords: Supply Chain, Big Data, Actionable Intelligence

Introduction

In this generation with a high level of connectivity through social channels, it's no surprise that companies are expecting quicker access to real-time information. One of the ways to achieve this kind of global visibility is through a supply chain operating network which is an inherent by-product of a Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) based, single instance, multi-tenant network. All of these information gathered through the network from numerous sources such as carriers, shippers, warehouses, etc., is bought together and then pooled which made them accessible easily by the end users. For optimizing loads, Shippers can join forces and also carriers can coordinate to lessen the empty miles and its consequences including carbon footprint. This ideology is similar to social networking where larger the network, greater the opportunity for collaboration.

SaaS is the Best

Companies of any size can be benefitted by the leverage of cloud computing and big data. This empowerment is possible through Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) solutions.

Thus SaaS subscriptions are mostly driven by this demand on big data analytics. Gartner, the Global research firm elucidate this information and also forecasts that in the next five years business performance of more than three quarters of global enterprises will be driven by advanced analytics which can be achieved through big data analytics. More than 60 to 70 percent of the new customers seek a cloud-based (SaaS) transportation management solution on the the 2016 Gartner Supply Chain Executive Conference. Business leaders are attracted to these appealing advantages possessed by SaaS model.

A Cloud-based Transport Management System alone is not enough for shifting the system to the multi advantageous SaaS solutions. More powerful in the reality is the base of network infrastructure which used to back up the cloud based TMS. Users who chose TMS solution based on SaaS approach along with the multiple tenants on a single instance can leverage the benefits rather than the users who believe mere shifting technology can bring out the transformation. One platform of technology which has a private access to countless customers brings out the opportunity to network among them to build the needed environment.

In the process of producing numerous transactions of freight movements among the thousands of supply chain participants by sharing information, an ecosystem of multi tenant environment can be created with single instance. This kind of ecosystem will keep on strengthening its environment when the network continues to involve more participants.

Other challenging task lies on connecting shippers, vessel carriers, forwarders, suppliers and also third party supply chain players. However, through this kind of SaaS-based Transport Management System these challenges can be overridden as the required connections are already been established in the cloud based TMS. These networks are very much beneficial during scenarios like natural calamities, extreme climatic changes, hurricane, flood, etc., All the end users of Transport Management System can obtain the information about blockage in the traffic, changes in the route and other telematics restrictions which are also conveyed to the drivers, delivery delays happening in warehouse docks are instantly relayed to real time stakeholders.

This allows for a quicker response and action towards the disruptions caused as all the end users and other stakeholders are well aware of the reason and thus the delay in schedule can be reduced through faster communication and response taken in the form of collaborative action to make the shipment back on track.

Is Big Data a Big Problem!

There is an expression, “Too much is never enough”. This phrase will not be suitable when it comes to big data. When we really don’t know the method of analyzing data, the availability of huge information will bring a overwhelming nature with the mountains of information. Still the recent research performed by Accenture identified that 97 percent of executives revealed that they have essential understanding of application of big data on their supply chain practices. In contrast to this statistics, only 17 percent of them have implemented the analytics in their supply chain functions.

FIGURE 1
Companies' Current Use of Big Data Analytics in the Supply Chain

In Figure 1, we can see a breakdown of how respondents reported using big data analytics. Participants of nearly 37 percent used to embed the TMS in the core areas of their supply chain practices whereas 37 percent used TMS only on the ad- hoc basis. Also 20 percent of the participants used TMS in few areas of supply chain that too in an ad hoc basis whereas the remaining 6 percent doesn’t use TMS in any of their supply chain functions.

Lack of proper team to support the big data analytics is the main reason for not using TMS as a supply chain strategy. Moreover it requires specialized skills to perform the computing like searching, locating, manipulating, controlling and diagnosing the interpretation and deriving the results through the data in an effective manner. Thus 34 percent of the companies possess an independent team of data scientists who used to focus only on these big data analytics. This robust team of TMS is fueled by the growing network with which cost savings can be achieved. Better business decisions can be taken with the help of Transport Management System which helps the driver with the hidden data about the supply chain.

Actionable Intelligence

Accumulating the Data, Making Analytics, Deriving the Decision and Execution in Action are the four steps involved in Actionable Intelligence. It is a process of continuous improvement. Companies which are not having specialized data analytic researchers can make use of this iterative process for increasing their supply chain functions. This iterative approach is complimented with the Transport Management System following single instance and multi-tenant approach. This will provide all the information regarding the transportation collected from multiple companies in the network and is used for real time benchmarking process. Transport Management System software also identify the trends which are statistical in nature and analyzed based on the simulation and modeling techniques.

Driving the Actionable Intelligence Cycle

Actionable intelligence can be used as a never ending process. It can shed light on the supply chain functional areas having problem (disruption from the routine) which need to be addressed in an immediate response.

1. The cycle starts with the first step which involves collection of data in to the Transport Management System. Source of the data, various types of data and the differing size are the variables determining the depth of the data collected into the TMS. As said previously, single instance, multi-tenant networking is the specialization of SaaS-based system which allows exhaust transportation data to be shared with all the stakeholders. Data from the private companies will be kept confidential. Network participants used to receive the information after the data is compiled and spread among the network as a benchmarking or historical trending information. Users can access their own data in private mode and there is an option for comparing it with the real-time industry data on screen. These options are exclusively offered by Transport Management System.

2. Data Analysis is the second step which involves comparison of real time industry benchmark information with the Knowledge Performance Indicators. This includes information on a company's moves on transportation related decisions along with the other participants among the network.

3. Followed by these steps, decision making is taken which is considered as the third step. Decision making is based on the uncovered information in the analytics and these decisions are strategic and also tactical in nature. Since Actionable Intelligence is considered as a constant cycle it can be used to solve the problems and starting the process again with an adjustment of the process/policy.

4. Final step is execution of the decision made and this involves many layers including specified procurement targeted towards particular segment, conversion of the mode and also different forms of optimization. This includes implementation of new production and minimizing supply chain costs through adoption of different sourcing schedules.

Actionable intelligence cycle will started again after the company goes through the final step of execution. Actionable intelligence gives the advantage to deepen the analytics to understand how well the supply chain functions are performed and also underlines the challenges faced by the managers. Thus more questions will be raised which are never considered before and thus execution became prime important process in Actionable Intelligence Cycle.

Actionable Intelligence in Action

India's largest milk producer which is considered as nation's prominent supplier once struggled with the problem of handling limited visibility in their overall networking. This drastically reduces the opportunities for them to collaborate internally. The company was struggling to leverage the fleet operations within a capacity constraint marketplace. They had a sizable fleet operation and they have gone through the same issues in leveraging the benefits

In this scenario actionable intelligence revealed some of the best practices among the environment which is aimed to build a centralized system in their organization. This includes shifting of various freight operations to different modes and increased utilization of freight with unlocked additional carrier capacity. This additional carrier capacity on the freight was induced through the best practices and this step was targeted to achieve increased revenue generation and collaboration opportunities within and outside the company.

The company used to gain cost control through this shifting in freight and was able to optimize and standardize the accessorial charges. By engaging this actionable intelligence, the organization then realized a reduction in accessorial charges nearly of 8 percent. Additional costs savings also realized with the visibility to round-trip the opportunities which are allowed in the company to negotiate lower rates with carriers, when marketplace conditions were doing the opposite. Along with this combination of these collaboration opportunities within the Transport Management System, the company was able to unlock the potential and thus it paves way for cost reductions and revenue opportunities, all while these summarize the efforts and leverage the business process outsourcing for the strategy, planning, and execution of their transportation.

Conclusion

SaaS Transportation Management System (TMS) solutions have made it feasible for businesses of all sizes to leverage big data for supply chain network optimization through actionable intelligence. Companies that use big data to improve their supply chain management processes have experienced these faster reaction times to supply chain disruptions, advanced supply chain efficiency, and better collaboration across discrete supply chains.

The transportation ecosystem created by this SaaS based single instance, multi-tenant environment creates the type of real-time industry data available only to connected network participants. Thus actionable intelligence will provide the competitive advantage to the business by poking holes in the current state and guiding to a new state where cost savings significantly impact the bottom line.

References

1. Big Data with Big Success Executive Summary, Accenture, (April 2014).
2. Gartner Says Modernization and Digital Transformation Projects Are Behind Growth in Enterprise Application Software Market. (August 27, 2015). Gartner Newsroom.
3. Sabitha Malli S., Vijayalakshmi S., Balaji V. (2018) Real Time Big Data Analytics to Derive Actionable Intelligence in Enterprise Applications. In: Dey N., Hassanien A., Bhatt C., Ashour A., Satapathy S. (eds) Internet of Things and Big Data Analytics Toward Next-Generation Intelligence. Studies in Big Data, vol 30. Springer, Cham